

Effects of modern Agriculture on Human Health

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Introduction:-

Agriculture is the major source in India. Above 65-70% population live hood depend on Agriculture. So India is one of the leading developing country making Economic progress through agricultural development In our post our population growth is low. But in past the population growth is very high. So we need to the present level of Agriculture production not reached the optional stage because of series of hurdles.

Agricultural farm workers are at a very high risk of occupational disease due to exposure to agrochemical resulting from inadequate education training and safety system in developed countries modern farming relies on many chemicals such as fertilizers pesticides and crop preservative to product and preserve and abundance of high quality food pesticides are chemical substances that derive their name from the French word 'pest' which means pest or plague and Latin word caldera to kill pesticide therefor can be defined on any chemical substance or mixture of substance intended preventing, destroying repelling or mitigating the effect of any pest plants animals. They include herbicides insecticides, rodenticides, fungicides mollusides, nematocides and attractants used in Agriculture.

Pesticide Effect on Human Health:-

Pesticide can causes shorter adverse health effects caused acute effects as well as chronic adverse Effects that can occur months or years after exposure. Examples of acute health effects include stinging Every rashes blisters blindness nausea dizziness, diarrhea and death. Examples of known chronic effects are cancers birth directs reproductive harm neurological and disruption of the endocrine system. Some people are more vulnerable than others to pesticide impacts. For example infants and young children are known to be more susceptible than adults to the toxic effects of pesticides. Farm workers and pesticide applicators are also more vulnerable because they receive grater exposures. Chronic include cancer and other tumors, brine and nervous system damage, birth defect. Infertility and other reproductive problems and damage to the liver, kidneys lungs and other body organs. Pesticide have been implicated in human studies or leukemia lymphoma and cancers of the brain breast Prostate testis and ovaries. Reproductive harm from pesticides includes birth defects still birth spontaneous Abortion sterility and in fertility. Similar impacts have been associated with human exposure to these chemicals.

Hormone Disruptions:-

Endometriosis Hypospadias undescended test ides precocious puberty in girls reduced sperm counts. Fertility problem. Epidemiological studies in humans indicated that there is a possible association between Pesticide exposure infertility breast prostate and ovarian cancer and nervous system concerns. The male farm walkers over so years of age the use of chlorinated pesticide and methyl bromide were significantly associated with prostate cancer the second most common cancer in men. After Lung cancer in their Indian on the pesticide induced.

These farmers has a very high private of chronic derma respiratory symptoms revealed that most of the farmers were poorly educated and use heavy pesticide, these farmers have a very high prevalence of chronic derma respiratory symptoms particularly cough pharyngitis. Bronchitis asthma respiratory insufficient dyspnea nasal catch sinusitis pharyngeal irrigation has several health problems such as Parkinson's disease disruption of glucose homeostasis have been linked with some intense diseases of exposure of pesticide. Agriculture effects on Human health

The agricultural sector has undergone immense change since the publication agriculture at RISK in 1988. In some respects there has been improvement in the health and safety of those working in agriculture due to improved technology personal protection and awareness of hazards. The establishment of the NIOSH Agriculture health and safety centers as a result of that effort has provided a network for the collaboration of academic health center researcher agricultural safety educators and agricultural engineers to institute a multi-disciplinary approach research outreach and education in agricultural health and sectary the regional centers appropriately reelect the geographic variation in farming. Conditions and practices regulatory approaches to improving occupational and environmental health in agricultural practices have included the passage of worker Footaction standard in 1992 and the food equality protection act in 1996 both dealing exclusively with pesticides. There is still much to be done however to prevent injuries and improve the health states of those working in agriculture. Even with the consolidation of agricultural operation and the increased complexity and size of forms and other agricultural operations there is a lack of knowledge of how

many people are adversely affected by their exposures particularly long term low level exposures. The majority of production operations are exempted from direct OSHA regulation and as a result the medical surveillance the oceans in other industries often does not or at best occurs sporadically in agriculture. The reporting system for occupational illness is still woefully inadequate which makes it almost impossible to accurately track trends determine long term adverse health effects from agricultural exposures. Farmers have an increased prevalence of many acute and chronic health conditions including cardiovascular and respiratory disease. Arthritis skin cancer hearing loss and amputation. Other health outcomes (C.B. rackbill Cameron Behrens 1994) Three prospective consort studies have been launched that will help answer some of questions.

There are many other health issues of concern that were not addressed in this paper including dermatitis and other zoonotic infections. topics discussed in detail were chosen because of the focus of current research and their potential of be the most affected by the changes occurring in agricultural advances in biotechnology, genetic modified organisms (GMOS) new agrochemicals and an evolving work force will continue to have an impact on the human health in agriculture and need to be addressed by future research.

Precautions to be taken from effect of modern agriculture

1. Government regulation

Keeping agriculture pollution in check is much harder than it seems. For the farmers to become clean once again levels of water, soil and industrial pollution have to be kept in check. Over the last decade or so Government have become stricter enforcing. Regulation.

2. Awareness of farmers.

Farmers often unknowingly cause the environmental system. Does by increasing the farmer's knowledge they should be taught that the excessive use of fertilizer and pesticide has a huge adverse impact on the whole ecosystem. Thus by increasing the Farmers knowledge and awareness agricultural pollution can be mitigated to the certain degree. They must know that the following points.

A) Applying the right quantity of pesticide and fertilizer that are necessary get a reasonable crop is yield.

B) Using crops to prevent bare ground. when the actual harvest is over thus preventing soil erosion and loss of waterways.

C) Planting grasses, trees and farmers along the edges of field that lies on the boundaries of water bodies. They could act as buffers and nutrient losses can be avoided by filtering out nutrient before

reaching field in order to reduce runoff, soil, compassion and erosion.

D) Animal waste is a big of agriculture pollution. The management of these pollutants is crucial.

E) Several manure treatment processing need to follow which aim to reduce the adverse impact of manure on the environmental system.

3. Changes in agriculture system.

Many farmers are moving back to traditional manure direct irrigation from local water bodies and organic means of keeping pest populations in check. But for the process of agriculture pollution to be fully reigned in there has to be a complete shift in the way agriculture is practiced.

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